

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF WATER SURFACE CLEANING DEVICE FOR WATER BODIES

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Abstract— Our project aimed at developing a cleaning device to clean lakes and ponds containing wastes like small water bottles, leaves, thermocols and cigarette butts etc., We developed an Iot (Internet of Things) based remote controlled device which consists of rack and pinion mechanisms to lift the trash using trash tray with the help of the dc geared motor attached to the motor frame on either side of the bot. A translatory mechanism consisting of rack and pinion is made for pushing the trash that is lifted at certain height into the trash bin which can even clean the algae of water by scrapping it. While trash is fallen into the trash bin the water particles are trapped into filter tub consisting of activated charcoal to reduce its pH level up to some extend and use that water for non-portable water needs. The analysis was carried for some of the critical components such as trash tray, motor frame and PVC pipe with the help of analysis software called “Ansys”. Results obtained that for a maximum of 10kg of load applied on the trash plate it exerts a bending stress of 65.783MPa and for a load of 1.47N acting on the motor frame it exerts a bending stress of 0.154MPa and for a load of 147.15N acting on the PVC it exerts a bending stress of 0.26MPa. The results shows that the values of the bending stresses obtained through analysis for the above components are less than the allowable range and hence its safe.

Keywords— Internet of Things, translatory mechanism, Ansys, bending stress.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water makes up over 71% of the earth's surface and is an essential resource for all living things [1]. Only 3 percent of it can be drunk, though. Water is a universal solvent that can dissolve a wide range of things, including chemicals, sewage, hazardous pollutants from factories, and more. As a result, human activity has seriously contaminated water, which is a major issue that all living things are currently dealing. The aquatic environment is harmed by the discharge of trash, sewage, and liquid waste from homes and chemical factories into bodies of water, which is the main source of this contamination. As a result, the water becomes unsafe to drink and endangers people's health.

One innovative solution to this problem is a concept of Iot based water surface cleaning device using Rack and pinion mechanisms. Here we intend to develop our device named "REVA Aqua Bot," as shown in fig. 1. The V-shape design in the front end of the device helps in collecting and guiding the floating waste toward the lifting tray of the device, which in turn lifts the waste upwards, and with the help of the Rack and pinion mechanism. The waste gets pushed into the trash collecting tray. The trash collecting tray has several holes towards the lower portion of the tray, through which the water coming with the waste gets filtered to the filtration unit of the device.

Fig. 1 REVA Aqua Bot

In the filtration unit, there is a pH sensor that detects the pH levels of the water incoming. There is activated charcoal present in the filter tub which will further help in filtering the incoming water through the bin. Activated charcoal used in REVA Aqua Bot helps in reducing the pH levels of water by 10% and the filter paper attached near the pipe's entrance at the edge of the filter tub ensures no particles pass through it. Thus, filtered water can further be used for agricultural purpose.

II. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of our project are as follows.

- To Design and Develop the Water Surface Cleaning Device for Water Bodies.
- To integrate pH sensor for determining the water acidity or alkalinity.
- To filter the water that is collected from the trash bin and making it suitable for the use of non-portable water needs.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

Shreejit Narayan Chaudhari et al [1] presented paper on “**Water Surface Solid Waste Cleaning Robot for Ponds**”. The prototype consisting of the conveyor belt is tested on an artificially created small pond with added solid waste such as plastic, tiny branches and leaves. It is observed that the maximum waste carrying capacity of the system is 300 gm and it can work continuously for one hour using lithium battery of 3.6 Watts.

Shreya Phirke et al [2] presented paper on “**Design of an Autonomous Water Cleaning Bot**”. The garbage collector box can collect up to 3–5 kg of garbage through the conveyor system in one cycle and to achieve autonomous based on garbage detection, the Raspberry Pi 3B along with Arduino UNO system is used to control the robot's movement towards garbage after analyzing if it's a garbage or non-garbage. After detecting the obstacle, the garbage classification was implemented using the YOLOv3 (You Only Look Once, version 3) object detection algorithm.

Hsing-Cheng Chang et al [3] presented paper on “**Autonomous Water Quality Monitoring and Water Surface Cleaning for Unmanned Surface Vehicle**”. SEN0161 pH sensor was used for water quality monitoring. Once the water pH value is higher than 8.5 or lower than 6.5, the water pump is driven to extract the water for cleaning residual liquid in the pumping pipe. The collected water samples are later analysed in specialized laboratories and during floating garbage detection, the success rate was found to be 100% when the floating garbage was in the visual angle ranged from -30° to 30° on the front of the device when the distances between the floating garbage and the device were 40cm and 70cm respectively. When the distance between the floating garbage and the device was 130 cm, the success rates of the floating garbage collection fell to 70% to 95% in different directions.

Anandakumar Haldorai et al [4] presented paper on “**An improved single short detection method for smart vision-based water garbage cleaning robot**”. USV employs a customized Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) algorithm for autonomous tracking and collection of floating debris on the water's surface. Remarkably, when the floating garbage falls within the visual range of -30° to 30° in front of the USV and when positioned between 45 and 75 cm from the USV, the success rate of debris identification reached 100%.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 2 Flow chart of Methodology

V. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

i. Design

The Design Calculations were carried out for some of the critical parts such as Trash Plate, Motor Frame and PVC pipe as shown below.

1. Design of Trash plate:

Consider one symmetrical portion of the trash plate having dimensions of 121mmx198mm.

The nominal stress equation is given by,

$$\sigma_{nom} = \frac{6M_b}{(w-d)h^2} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$\text{Bending moment } M_b \text{ is given by } \frac{wL^2}{8} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Substituting eq,2 in 1 we get

$$\sigma_{nom} = \frac{6w \left(\frac{wL^2}{8} \right)}{(w-d)h^2} \dots\dots\dots 3$$

let's assume 10kg weight (W) is distributed uniformly over the trash plate.

Then load intensity is given by.

$$w = \frac{W}{L} \dots\dots\dots 4$$

Now,

$$w = \frac{10 \times 9.81}{198} = 0.495 \frac{N}{mm}$$

Substituting value of w in eq.3 we get

$$\sigma_{nom} = \frac{6 \times 0.495 \times 198^2}{8 \left(\frac{242}{2} - 5 \right) \times 3^2}$$

$$\sigma_{nom} = 14 \text{ MPa}$$

Now,

$$\frac{d}{w} = \frac{5}{\left(\frac{242}{2}\right)} = 0.041$$

$$\frac{d}{h} = \frac{5}{3} = 1.667$$

The K_σ value corresponding to $\frac{d}{w}$ and $\frac{d}{h}$ is given by.

$$K_\sigma = 2.15$$

The above value is obtained using the graph of stress concentration factor for a plate with transverse circular hole subjected to bending.

Now the stress concentration factor is given by

$$K_\sigma = \frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{nom}} \dots\dots\dots 5$$

On Substituting the K and σ_{nom} value in eq 5 we get

$$\sigma_{max} = K * \sigma_{nom} = 2.15 * 14 = 30.1 \text{ MPa}$$

Considering whole plate

$$\sigma_{max} * 2 = 60.2 \text{ MPa}$$

2. Design of Motor Frame:

Consider dimensions of the motor frame of 180mmx90mm

The load of 1.4715N is distributed on the entire surface.

Load intensity is given by

$$w = \frac{1.4715}{180} = 8.175 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N/mm} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Then bending moment is given by

$$M_b = \frac{wL^2}{8} = \frac{8.175 \times 10^{-3} \times 180^2}{8} = 33.108 \text{ N-mm} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Bending equation is given by

$$\frac{M_b}{I} = \frac{\sigma}{y} \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Substituting the respective values to find bending stress we get,

$$\frac{33.108}{\frac{90 \times 3^3}{12}} = \frac{\sigma}{1.5}$$

$$\sigma = 0.2452 \text{ MPa}$$

Out of 180mm, 120mm is occupied by triangular strength piece.

Therefore only 66.6% of the bending is considered.

Hence by multiplying this 0.667 as a factor we get.

$$\sigma = 0.667 * 0.2452$$

$$\sigma = 0.174 \text{ MPa}$$

3. Design of PVC Pipe

The pipe has an outer diameter of 110mm and inner diameter of 104mm and the length of 1200mm.

Bending load is given by.

$$M_b = \frac{wL}{24} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$w = \omega L$$

$$\omega = \frac{15 \times 9.81}{1200}$$

$$w = \frac{15 \times 9.81}{1200} * 1200 = 147.15$$

$$M_b = \frac{147.15 \times 1200}{24} = 7357.5 \text{ Nmm}$$

Bending equation is given by.

$$\frac{M_b}{I} = \frac{\sigma}{y} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

$$\frac{7357 \cdot 5}{64 (110^4 - 104^4)} = \frac{\sigma}{55}$$

$\sigma = 0.28 \text{ MPa}$

ii. Analysis

The analysis of the parts such as Trash Plate, Motor Frame and PVC pipe was carried out using the analysis software called “ANSYS WORKBENCH”. Here we focused on getting the Equivalent stress (von-Mises) for the above said parts.

1. Equivalent stress for Trash Plate:

Fig. 3 Equivalent stress (von-Mises stress) of Trash Plate

The von-Mises stress of the Trash Plate is found to be 65.78MPa as shown in fig. 3, which is within the property of the material when a pressure of 2.049e-3MPa is applied to the surface of the Trash Plate.

2. Equivalent stress for Motor Frame:

Fig. 4 Equivalent stress (von-Mises stress) of Motor Frame

The von-Mises stress of the Motor Frame is found to be 0.154MPa as shown in fig. 4, which is within the property of the material when a pressure of 2.049e-3MPa is applied to the surface of the Motor frame.

3. Equivalent stress for PVC pipe:

Fig. 5 Equivalent stress (von-Mises stress) of PVC Pipe

The von-Mises stress of the PVC Pipe is found to be 0.26MPa as shown in fig. 5, which is within the property of the material when a udl (uniformly distributed load) of 0.122N/mm is applied to the surface of the PVC Pipe.

TABLE. 1 Comparison between Theoretical and ANSYS Solution

Part Name	Theoretical stress in MPa	ANSYS solution in MPa	Error %
Trash Plate	60.2	65.78	9.27
Motor Frame	0.17	0.15	5.81
PVC pipe	0.28	0.26	4.39

As shown in table. 1, the error values for the respective parts are within the allowable limit. Hence can be used.

VI. FABRICATION

We used acrylic and PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride) material to build the model with the dimensions of length of 1371mm, height of 693mm and width of 650mm. The below fig. 6 shows the final fabricated model.

Fig. 6 Final Fabricated Model

VII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the stress analysis, the von-Mises stress for the critical parts such as Trash Plate, Motor Frame and PVC pipes are all under the allowable limit of their respective materials.

1. *Cleaning:*

Our model was developed to clean only the surface waste garbage such as small plastic bottles, dry leaves, cigarette butts etc., floating on the water bodies such as lakes and ponds. We tested our model in the pond located at nelamangala town (Bengaluru rural district). As illustrated in fig. 7, the waste gets accumulated at the front portion of the bot, where further it is lifted by the rack and pinion mechanism and pushed by using the translatory mechanism.

Fig. 7 Surface waste Cleaning Process

2. *Purification:*

The filter unit consists of activated charcoal, which filters the water particles by the method of adsorption. Further a filter paper is used near the outlet pipe to remove the water which can be used for other non-portable water needs. As shown in the fig. 8 the results indicates that the water colour and quality is improved up to some extent.

Fig. 8 Purification of wastewater

3. *pH Monitoring:*

Here, we intend to monitor the pH level of the water in the filter unit by using the analogue pH sensor. It monitors the real time pH value of the water filtered and delivers it to the user with the help of the mobile application called Blynk app as shown in the fig. 9 below. So that it can be decided for the use of non-portable water needs. The pH sensor gives the concentration reading from 1-14 indicating that 0-6 as acidic, 7 as neutral and 8-14 as basic.

Fig. 9 pH monitoring using Blynk application.

While testing in the pond, the pH value indicated was 13.594 in the filter unit as shown in fig. 16, which is more basic in nature.

4. *Range and Operation:*

The 2.4 GHz nodemcu ESP8266 Wi-Fi module has the range of approximately 50-60m while connected to mobile phone through hotspot and whereas the operation time of the 4.4A/h Lithium-polymer battery was about 35-40 minutes roughly based on load variations.

Conclusions

- i. The stresses acting on the critical components such as trash Plate, Motor Frame and PVC Pipe were found to be lesser than the allowable stress of the materials used respectively.
- ii. The filtration unit was able to filter the water particles up to some extent and could use it for non-portable water needs and meanwhile the pH sensor was also capable of providing the real time data accurately.
- iii. For a single charge, the battery had the capacity of lasting for approximately 35-40min under full load conditions with the range of operating under 50-60m with the help of ESP8266 node-mcu Wi-Fi module.

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